

Metal complexes of some peptide derivatives. Part-XV. Mixed ligand complex formation of copper(II) with some *N*-benzenesulfonyldipeptides as primary ligands and acetate, 2-methylbenzimidazole, glycinate and bipyridine as secondary ligands

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Potentiometric investigation on the complex formation equilibria of Cu^{II} with *N*-benzenesulfonyl derivatives of some dipeptides, viz glycyglycine, glycy β -alanine and β -alanylglycine, hereafter, abbreviated as NBSGG, NBSGB and NBSBG (AH₂) respectively, in the presence of typical secondary ligands, viz acetate (ac-), 2-methylbenzimidazole (bz), glycinate (gly-) and bipyridine (bipy), hereafter, B, provides evidence of formation of varieties of binary and ternary complexes of the types Cu(AH), Cu(H₁AH), Cu(H₁A), Cu(H₁₋₁A)(OH), Cu(B), Cu(B)(AH), Cu(B)(H₁AH) and Cu(B)(H₁A). Stability constants of the complexes at 25 ± 1°, in aqueous solution at a constant ionic strength, I = 0.1 M (NaNO₃) have been determined and the complex formation equilibria elucidated on the basis of speciation curves. The sulfonamidodipeptide ligands (AH₂) provide three coordinating groups -COOH, -CONH-, and -SO₂NH-, and show ambidentism in forming the binary and the ternary complexes depending upon the denticity, σ -basicity and π -acidity of the B-ligands. The ternary complexes are found to be stable in the intermediate pH range (5–8). Above pH 8, the mixed ligand complexes derived from all the AH₂ and B ligands decompose to produce either the fully deprotonated binary complexes, Cu(H₁A)⁻ or the ternary hydroxo complexes Cu(H₁A)(OH)²⁻ depending upon the nature of the B-ligands.

Mixed ligands complex formation equilibria of biological metal ions with amino acids dipeptides and their derivatives provide useful models for metal – protein equilibria of relevance to the enzymic systems. Many of these mixed ligand complexes are suitable for mimicking the roles of metal ions in the active sites of metalloenzymes, studying the toxic effects of metal ions, detoxification mechanisms and drug designing¹. With a view to study the effect of the presence of medicinally active sulfonamide (-SO₂NH-) group in a chelating position on the modes of coordination of the peptide (-CONH-) group in dipeptide derivatives, in the presence of typical mono- and bidentate (O,N) and (N,N) donor ligands, we describe in this paper the results of an equilibrium study on the mixed ligand complex formation of Cu^{II} with *N*-benzenesulfonyl derivatives of glycyglycine (NBSGG), -glycy β -alanine (NBSGB) and - β -alanylglycine (NBSBG), (I), hereafter, AH₂, in the presence of acetate (ac-), 2-methylbenzimidazole (bz), glycinate (gly-) and bipyridine (bipy), hereafter, B, in aqueous solution at a constant ionic strength, I = 0.1 M (NaNO₃) at 25 ± 1°

Stability constants of the mixed ligand complexes have been correlated with the possible modes of coordination of the sulfonamidodipeptide ligands, size of the chelate rings, σ -basicity and π -acidity of the B-ligands.

Results and Discussion

Mixed ligand complex formation equilibria between Cu^{II}, AH₂ and B-ligands may be described according to

$$\beta_{pqr} = \frac{[\text{Cu}_p(\text{AH})_q(\text{B})_r(\text{OH})_s]}{[\text{Cu}]^p[\text{AH}]^q[\text{B}]^r[\text{OH}]^s} \quad (1b)$$

where, p, q and r are all positive integers, s is a negative

integer for a protonated species, positive integer for a deprotonated or a hydroxo species and zero for a neutral species². Charges are occasionally not shown for clarity. In the present systems, for the ligand species AH⁻, H₋₁AH²⁻, A²⁻ and H₋₁A³⁻ the values of *s* are -2, -1, -1 and 0, respectively. In dilute solution, only the mononuclear complexes (*p* = 1) are formed. Since the molar ratios of Cu^{II} : AH₂ : B have always been 1 : 1 : 1, therefore, for the present systems, *p* = *q* = *r* = 1. Stoichiometry of the different binary and ternary complexes, considered in calculating the formation constants of Cu^{II}-AH₂-B complexes, are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Stoichiometry of the binary and ternary complexes in the Cu^{II}-AH₂-B systems*

AH ₂ = NBSGG, NBSGB and NBSBG and B = ac-, bz, gly- and bipy	<i>p</i>	<i>q</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>s</i>
Cu _{<i>p</i>} (AH) _{<i>q</i>} (B) _{<i>r</i>} (OH) _{<i>s</i>}				
AH ₂	0	1	0	-3
AH	0	1	0	-2
A	0	1	0	-1
BH ₂	0	0	1	-2
BH	0	0	1	-1
B	0	0	1	0
Cu	1	0	0	0
Cu(AH)	1	1	0	-2
Cu(H ₋₁ AH)	1	1	0	-1
Cu(H ₋₁ A)	1	1	0	0
Cu(B)	1	0	1	0
Cu(AH)(B)	1	1	1	-2
Cu(H ₋₁ AH)(B)	1	1	1	-1
Cu(H ₋₁ A)(B)	1	1	1	0
Cu(H ₋₁ A)(OH)	1	1	0	1

*Charges are not shown for simplicity.

Complex formation equilibria of Cu^{II} with the AH₂, bipy and gly- ligands start at pH values much lower than the pH-range of hydrolytic equilibria of Cu²⁺(aq.) ions. Therefore, the binary hydroxo complexes, Cu(OH)⁺, Cu(OH)₂ etc. are not involved in the formation equilibria of the mixed ligand complexes with these ligands. Hydroxo complex formations have of course been considered in calculating the stability constants of the binary Cu^{II}-B and ternary Cu^{II}-AH₂-B complexes with B = ac-, and bz. Formation constants of the complexes have been refined over several cycles and the values corresponding to minimum standard deviation (±0.02-0.05) are accepted (Tables 2-5). Complex formation equilibria have been elucidated on the basis of the speciation curves (Figs. 1-4) of the complexes, obtained as computer outputs².

Table 2. Formation constants^a of ternary Cu^{II}-ac-AH₂ (NBSGG, NBSGB and NBSBG) complexes in aqueous solution

Temp. = 25±1°, <i>I</i> = 0.1 M (NaNO ₃)			
$pK_{\text{acH}}^{\text{H}} = 4.60, \log K_{\text{Cu(ac)}}^{\text{Cu}} = 3.25$			
AH ₂	NBSGG	NBSGB	NBSBG
$\log K_{\text{Cu+AH}}^{2\text{H}}$	-8.50	-7.93	-10.30
$\log K_{\text{Cu(AH)}}^{\text{Cu}}$	2.75	2.92	3.48
$\log K_{\text{Cu(AH)(ac)}}^{\text{Cu}}$	4.63	6.57	6.98
$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$	-1.37	+0.40	+0.25
$\log K_{\text{Cu(ac)+AH}}^{2\text{H}}$	-8.83	-9.69	-11.33
$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{H}}$	-0.33	-1.76	-1.03
$\log K_{\text{Cu(H-1A)}}^{\text{H}}$	-9.25	-9.12	-9.71
$\log K_{\text{d}}$	-12.17	-10.61	-11.93

^aLimits of error = ± (0.02-0.05) in log unit.

Table 3. Formation constants^a of Cu^{II}-bz-AH₂ (NBSGG, NBSGB and NBSBG) complexes, where, bz = 2-methylbenzimidazole in aqueous solution

Temp 25±1°, <i>I</i> = 0.1 M (NaNO ₃)			
$pK_{\text{bzH}}^{\text{H}} = 6.75, \log K_{\text{Cu(bz)}}^{\text{Cu}} = 4.75$			
AH ₂	NBSGG	NBSGB	NBSBG
$\log K_{\text{Cu(AH)}}^{\text{Cu}}$	2.75	2.92	3.48
$\log K_{\text{Cu(bz)(AH)}}^{\text{Cu}}$	5.36	6.59	6.66
$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$	-2.14	-0.08	-1.57
$\log K_{\text{Cu+AH}}^{2\text{H}}$	-8.50	-7.93	-10.30
$\log K_{\text{Cu(bz)AH}}^{2\text{H}}$	-10.67	-9.98	-11.90
$\log K_{\text{Cu(AH)}}^{\text{H}}$	-5.35	-5.21	-6.45
$\log K_{\text{Cu(bz)(AH)}}^{\text{H}}$	-4.75	-5.14	-5.51
$\log K_{\text{Cu(H-1AH)}}^{\text{H}}$	-5.40	-5.64	-7.33
$\log K_{\text{Cu(bz)(H-1AH)}}^{\text{H}}$	-6.54	-6.68	-8.30
$\log K_{\text{d}}$	-11.83	-11.82	-12.86
$\log K_{\text{Cu(H-1A)}}^{\text{H}}$	-9.25	-9.12	-9.91

^aLimits of error = ±(0.02-0.5) in log unit.

Table 4. Formation constants^a of Cu^{II}-gly-AH₂ (NBSGG, NBSGB and NBSBG) complex in aqueous solution

Temp. = 25±1°, <i>I</i> = 0.1 M (NaNO ₃)			
$pK_{\text{gly-H}_2}^{\text{H}} = 1.85, pK_{\text{glyH}}^{\text{H}} = 9.60, \log K_{\text{Cu(gly)}}^{\text{Cu}} = 8.39$			
AH ₂	NBSGG	NBSGB	NBSBG
$\log K_{\text{Cu+AH}}^{2\text{H}}$	-8.50	-7.93	-10.30
$\log K_{\text{Cu(gly)+AH}}^{2\text{H}}$	-8.14	-7.78	-10.53
$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$	+0.36	+0.15	-0.23
$\log K_{\text{Cu(AH)}}^{\text{Cu}}$	2.75	2.92	3.48
$\log \beta_{\text{Cu(AH)(gly)}}^{\text{Cu}}$	11.69	11.48	12.09
$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$	+0.55	+0.17	+0.22
$\log K_{\text{Cu(AH)(gly)}}^{\text{Cu}}$	8.94	8.56	8.61
$\log K_{\text{d}}$	-10.59	-9.81	-12.29
$\log K_{\text{Cu(H-1A)}}^{\text{H}}$	-9.25	-	-

^aLimits of error = ±(0.02-0.05) in log unit.

Table 5. Formation constants^d of Cu^{II}-bipy-AH (NBSGG, NBSGB and NBSBG) complexes in aqueous solution

AH ₂	NBSGG	NBSGB	NBSBG
Temp. = 25±1°, I = 0.1 M (NaNO ₃)			
$pK_{\text{bipyH}_2}^{\text{H}} = 1.50$, $pK_{\text{bipyH}}^{\text{H}} = 4.65$, $\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})}^{\text{Cu}}$ = 9.50			
$\log K_{\text{Cu}+\text{AH}}^{\text{Cu}2\text{H}}$	-8.50	-7.93	-10.30
$\log \beta_{\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}-1\text{A})}^{\text{Cu}}$	2.96	2.89	0.30
$\log \beta_{\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}-1\text{A})}^{\text{Cu}}$	-6.54	-6.61	-9.20
$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$	+1.96	+1.32	+1.10
$\log K_{\text{d}}$	-18.00	-17.43	-19.80

^dLimits of error = ±(0.02~0.05) in log unit.**Fig. 2.** Speciation curves of 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : NBSGG (AH₂) : bz-system : (1) AH₂, (2) AH⁻, (5) bzH⁺, (6) bz, (7) Cu²⁺, (8) Cu(AH)⁺, (9) Cu(H₋₁AH), (10) Cu(H₋₁A)⁻, (11) Cu(bz)²⁺, (12) Cu(AH)(bz)⁺, (13) Cu(H₋₁AH)(bz), (14) Cu(H₋₁A)(bz)⁻, (15) Cu(H₋₁A)(OH)²⁻.

In the absence of Cu^{II} all the three sulfonamidopeptide ligands, viz. NBSGG, NBSGB and NBSBG titrate as diprotic acids (AH₂) due to deprotonation of the COOH and the SO₂NH groups ($pK_{\text{COOH}}^{\text{H}}$, 3.5~4.5; $pK_{\text{SO}_2\text{NH}}$,

Fig. 4. Speciation curves of 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : NBSGG (AH₂) : bipy system : (1) AH₂, (2) AH⁻, (6) bipy, (10) Cu(H₋₁A)⁻, (11) Cu(bipy)²⁺, (14) Cu(H₋₁A)(bipy)⁻.

9.6~10.6) in successive steps³. The peptide group (-CONH-) remains neutral in the absence of Cu^{II} in the entire pH-range studied. The fact that acetylglycine (CH₃CONHCH₂COOH) titrates as a monoprotic acid (AH) due to ionisation of the COOH group under the identical experimental condition, provides further evidence of neutrality of the CONH group as well as deprotonation of the SO₂NH group of the (AH₂) ligands in the second step.

Three types of complexes, viz. Cu(AH)⁺, Cu(H₋₁AH) and Cu(H₋₁A)⁻ are formed³ in the 1 : 1 binary Cu^{II} : AH₂ systems. In the Cu(AH)⁺ complexes (II), formed at the early stages of the reaction (pH < 4), the AH⁻ ions coordinate Cu^{II} as (N,O) bidentate ligands, using the neutral sulfamide N-atom and the amide carbonyl O-atom. The ionised carboxylate group fails to coordinate Cu^{II} due to angle strain in 7/8-membered chelate rings. With rise of pH (> 4.5), these (N, O) coordinated Cu(AH)⁺ complexes undergo deprotonation

of the amide (-CONH-) group with concomitant substitution of the amide carbonyl O-atom by the deprotonated amide N-atom involving a structural change (eqm 2) within the complex³⁻⁵. This brings the carboxylate O-atom at a position suitable for coordination of Cu^{II} in the resulting Cu(H₋₁AH) complexes (III). This structural change transforms the (N,O) bidentate AH⁻ ligand ion into (N,N⁻,O⁻) terdentate H₋₁AH²⁻ ion, consequently the λ_{max} (log ε) of Cu^{II} shows a blue shift from 740 (0.5) to 645 nm (2.03)⁶⁻⁹.

On further rise of pH (>8), the coordinated sulfonamide (-SO₂NH-) groups in the Cu(H₋₁AH) complexes (III) are deprotonated to produce the (N⁻,N⁻,O⁻) terdentate chelated Cu(H₋₁A)⁻ complexes (IV). At still higher pH values, the Cu(H₋₁A)⁻ complexes are hydrolysed to produce the ternary hydroxo complexes, Cu(H₋₁A)(OH)²⁻ (V)³.

The most predominant mixed ligand complexes formed in the 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : AH₂ : B systems, with B = ac⁻, bz, gly and bpy are Cu(AH)(B), Cu(H₋₁AH)(B) and Cu(H₋₁A)(B), in which the AH⁻, H₋₁AH²⁻ and H₋₁A³⁻ ligand species provide respectively (N,O) bidentate chelation using the neutral sulfonamide N-atom and amide carbonyl O-atom, (N,N⁻,O⁻) terdentate chelation using neutral sulfonamide N-, deprotonated amide N- and carboxylate O-atoms, (N⁻,N⁻,O⁻) terdentate chelation using the deprotonated sulfonamide N-, deprotonated amide N- and carboxylate

O-atoms, in the same manner as they coordinate Cu^{II} in the corresponding binary complexes (II, III and IV) respectively

1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : AH₂ : ac-systems

The major Cu^{II} containing species below pH 7 are the binary Cu(ac)⁺ and Cu(AH)⁺ complexes, which with rise of pH above 7 produce the ternary Cu(H₋₁A)(ac)²⁻ complexes according to eqms (3)–(5) as may be evident from the speciation curves (Fig. 1),

The values of log K_{Cu(ac)+AH}^{2H} (eqm 3) and log K_{Cu+AH}^{2H} are obtained as computer outputs. The Δ log K_{Cu}^H values corresponding to eqm (5) may be calculated using relation (6),

$$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{H}} = \log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{ac})+\text{AH}}^{2\text{H}} - \log K_{\text{Cu}+\text{AH}}^{2\text{H}} \quad (6)$$

Reaction (3) is found to be most favoured with NBSBG but least favoured with NBSGG, whereas, the reverse is true for reactions (4) and (5). The most predominant Cu^{II}-containing species at still higher pH values (pH >8) are the ternary hydroxo complexes, Cu(H₋₁A)(OH)²⁻, produced due to hydrolysis of binary Cu(H₋₁A)⁻ complexes and decomposition of ternary Cu(H₋₁A)(ac)²⁻ complexes according to eqms (7) and (8), respectively,

The K_{Cu(H-1A)}^H values (eqm 7) may be obtained as computer output, whereas the log K_d values (eqm 8) may be calculated using relation (9),

$$\log K_{\text{d}} = \log K_{\text{Cu}+\text{AH}}^{2\text{H}} + \log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})}^{\text{H}} - \log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{ac})}^{\text{H}} - \log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{ac})+\text{AH}}^{2\text{H}} \quad (9)$$

As the log K_d values (Table 2) imply, the Cu(H₋₁A)(ac)²⁻ complex derived from NBSGG is the one most reluctant to undergo dissociation (eqm 8)

1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : AH₂ : bz systems

None of the expected ternary complexes, viz Cu(bz)-(AH)⁺, Cu(bz)(H₋₁AH) and Cu(bz)(H₋₁A)⁻ are formed in significant amounts in these systems. The binary complexes Cu(bz)²⁻ and Cu(AH)⁺ prevail at lower pH values (pH <6). The Cu(H₋₁AH) complexes occur in the pH-range (4–7)

but their concentrations never exceed ~10–15%. The fully deprotonated binary $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})^-$ complexes dominate the pH-range of biological significance, $6 < \text{pH} < 8$. However, with the ligand NBSBG, the region above pH 6.5 could not be followed due to commencement of precipitation possibly of some electroneutral species, $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{AH})$ or $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{AH})$ or their mixtures. Speciation curves (Fig. 2) of the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}-\text{bz}-\text{AH}_2$ systems indicate the formation of the ternary complexes according to eqms. (10–12),

At much higher pH values ($\text{pH} > 8$), the ternary hydroxo complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})(\text{OH})^{2-}$ become increasingly important. Rise in the concentration of the bz ligand, after the initial decline due to complex formation (eqms. 10–12) and a 'stiff rise' in the concentration of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})(\text{OH})^{2-}$, indicate the formation of the latter from hydrolysis of $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})^-$ according to (eqm. 7) and also from the dissociation of the ternary complex $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})(\text{bz})^-$ according to (eqm. 13),

Formation constants (Table 3) of the complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})^{2+}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{AH})^+$, $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{AH})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})^-$, $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})(\text{OH})^{2-}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{AH})^+$, $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{AH})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})^-$ may be obtained as computer outputs. The dissociation constant (K_d) of the complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})^-$, eqm. (13), may be calculated using the relation (14),

$$\log K_d = \log K_{\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} + \text{AH}_2}^{2\text{H}} + \log K_{\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{H}-1\text{A})}^{\text{II}} - \log K_{\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{bz}) + \text{AH}}^{2\text{H}} + \log K_{\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{bz})}^{\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{bz})} \quad (14)$$

Benzimidazoles coordinate metal ions using the tertiary N-atom of the heteroaromatic system^{10–12}. Despite the possibility of synergistic stabilisation of the metal-ligand bonds due to strong σ -basicity of the ligands AH^- , $\text{H}_{-1}\text{AH}^{2-}$ and $\text{H}_{-1}\text{A}^{3-}$, and π -acidity of the bz ring system, none of the ternary $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}-\text{bz}-\text{AH}_2$ complexes are more stable relative to the hydroxo complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})(\text{OH})^{2-}$, possibly due to steric crowding by the benzenesulfonyl and 2-methylbenzimidazole moieties around the Cu^{II} coordination sphere (VI, VII). Ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{AH})^+$ complexes (VI) are converted through $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{AH})$ (VII) to $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})^-$ complexes due to successive deprotonation of the coordinated amide ($-\text{CONH}-$) and sulfonamide ($-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}-$) groups in the same manner as the binary $\text{Cu}(\text{AH})^+$ complexes (II) are

transformed into $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{A})^-$ complexes (IV) through $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{AH})$ complexes (III).

It is, however, interesting to note that the metal-promoted amide deprotonation in the ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{AH})^+$ complexes occurs at comparatively lower pH values than the corresponding binary $\text{Cu}(\text{AH})^+$ complexes. π -Acidity of the delocalised aromatic system of the bz ligand, possibly coordinated *trans* to the amide moiety, favourably shifts the eqm., (VI) $\rightleftharpoons$ (VII), to right and thus may be responsible for comparatively higher acidity of the amide proton in the $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{AH})^+$ complexes (VI). However, acidity of sulfonamide proton in the $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{AH})$ complexes (VII) shows no enhancement over those of the corresponding binary $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{AH})$ complexes (III), possibly due to non-existence of any π -interaction between the coordinated sulfonamide group and the bz ligand through Cu^{2+} in this mode of coordination. Lower acidity of sulfonamide proton in the ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{AH})$ complexes relative to the binary $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{AH})$ complexes may be attributed to the higher σ -basicity of the bz ligand relative to coordinated H_2O molecules in the latter.

1. 1. 1 $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}-\text{AH}_2$, gly-systems

The major Cu^{II} -containing species below pH 7 are the binary complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{AH})^+$, $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})^+$ and the ternary complexes, $\text{Cu}(\text{AH})(\text{gly})$. As the speciation curves (Fig. 3) of $\text{Cu}(\text{AH})^+$, glyH and $\text{Cu}(\text{AH})(\text{gly})$ imply, the ternary complexes are formed according to eqm. (15),

The values of $\log K_{\text{Cu(AH)(gly)}}^{\text{Cu}}$ and $\log K_{\text{Cu(gly)}}^{\text{Cu}}$ are found to be close (Table 4), suggesting bidentate (NH_2 , COO^-) chelation¹³ of Cu^{II} by the gly- ligand to the Cu(AH)^+ complexes, in which Cu^{II} is already (N,O) bidentate chelated by the AH^- ion through the neutral sulfonamide N-atom and the amide carbonyl O-atom. Above pH 7, the fully deprotonated ternary complexes, $\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{A)}(\text{gly})^{2-}$, are formed according to eqm. (16),

The $\log K_{\text{Cu(gly)+AH}}^{2\text{H}}$ values (Table 4), although slightly higher, are almost of the same order of magnitude as the $\log K_{\text{Cu+AH}}^{2\text{H}}$ values. This suggests an identical mode of coordination by the $\text{H}_{-1}\text{A}^{3-}$ ligand species in the binary $\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{A)}^-$ and in the ternary $\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{A)}(\text{gly})^{2-}$ complexes, i.e. terdentate ($\text{N}^-, \text{N}^-, \text{O}^-$) chelation by the deprotonated sulfonamide N-, deprotonated amide N- and carboxylate O-atoms giving a five-coordinated geometry (VIII) around Cu^{II} in the ternary $\text{Cu(gly)(H}_{-1}\text{A)}^{2-}$ complexes, in which the COO^- group of the gly- ligand possibly provides axial coordination¹⁴. However, due to the profound tendency of Cu^{II} to achieve square-planer coordination and strong terdentate mode of chelation by the $\text{H}_{-1}\text{A}^{3-}$ ligand ions, quite a good amount (~50%) of Cu^{II} remains in the form of the binary $\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{A)}^-$ complexes, formed above pH 5.5 possibly, due to dissociation of the ternary Cu(AH)(gly) complexes according to eqm. (17),

and also in the form of the ternary hydroxo complexes $\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{A)}(\text{OH})^{2-}$, formed above pH 7.5, according to eqms. (7) and (8). The hydrolysis constant $K_{\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{A)}}^{\text{H}}$ (eqm. 7) may be obtained as computer output and the dissociation constant, K_d (eqm. 17) may be calculated using relation (18),

$$\log K_d = \log K_{\text{Cu+AH}}^{2\text{H}} - \log \beta_{\text{Cu(AH)(gly)}}^{\text{Cu}} - \log K_{\text{gly}}^{\text{H}} \quad (18)$$

1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : AH_2 : bipy systems :

In all the 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : AH_2 : bipy systems ($\text{AH}_2 = \text{NBSGG}$, NBSGB and NBSBG), 100% of Cu^{II} exists as Cu(bipy)^{2+} at the very early stages (pH ~2) of the reactions. The only Cu^{II} -containing species above pH 7 are the ternary complexes $\text{Cu(bipy)(H}_{-1}\text{A)}^-$, which as the speciation curves (Fig. 4) imply, are formed out of the binary complex, Cu(bipy)^{2+} and AH^- according to eqm. (19),

$\log \beta_{\text{Cu(bipy)(H}_{-1}\text{A)}}^{2\text{H}}$ values (Table 5) are obtained as com-

puter output, $\log K_{\text{Cu(bipy)+AH}}^{2\text{H}}$ values (eqm. 19) may be calculated using relation (20),

$$\log K_{\text{Cu(bipy)+AH}}^{2\text{H}} = \log \beta_{\text{Cu(bipy)(H}_{-1}\text{A)}}^{2\text{H}} - \log K_{\text{Cu(bipy)}}^{\text{Cu}} \quad (20)$$

$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ values of the ternary $\text{Cu(bipy)(H}_{-1}\text{A)}^-$ complexes may be calculated using relation (21),

$$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}} = \log K_{\text{Cu(bipy)+AH}}^{2\text{H}} - \log K_{\text{Cu+AH}}^{2\text{H}} \quad (21)$$

π -Acidic nature of the bipy ligand is responsible for high positive (~+2) values of $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ in these complexes. Strongly (N,N) bidentate coordinating bipy ligand engages two positions around Cu^{II} and forces the $\text{H}_{-1}\text{A}^{3-}$ ligand species to coordinate Cu^{II} as a (N^-, N^-) bidentate ligand to form the $\text{Cu(bipy)(H}_{-1}\text{A)}^-$ complexes (IX) having square-planar $\text{Cu(N,N)(N}^-, \text{N}^-)$ geometry due to favourable tetragonal distortion. The $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ values of ternary $\text{Cu(bipy)(H}_{-1}\text{A)}^-$ complexes with $\text{AH}_2 = \text{NBSGG}$ and NBSGB are comparable, but are higher than the $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ value, of the corresponding NBSBG complex. This is obvious, since the (N^-, N^-) bidentate chelating $\text{H}_{-1}\text{A}^{3-}$ ligand species derived from NBSGB ($x = 1$) form five-membered strain-free chelate rings without double bond, whereas that derived from NBSBG ($x = 2$) forms a six-membered chelate ring without any double bond, which is less stable due to angle strain¹.

The speciation curves (Fig. 4) of the Cu(bipy)^{2+} , $\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{A)}^-$, and bipy indicate formation of small amount (~10%) of the binary $\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{A)}^-$ complexes through the displacement of the bipy ligand at higher pH values (pH 7) according to eqm. (22),

of which the equilibrium constant (K_d) may be related to the formation constants of the binary Cu(bipy)^{2+} and $\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{A)}^-$ complexes according to eqn. (23),

$$\log K_d = \log K_{\text{Cu+AH}}^{2\text{H}} - \log K_{\text{Cu(bipy)}}^{\text{Cu}} \quad (23)$$

The order of $\log K_d$ values is compatible with the order of stability constant of binary $\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{A)}^-$ and ternary $\text{Cu(bipy)(H}_{-1}\text{A)}^-$ complexes (Table 5).

Experimental

The sulfonamidodipeptide ligands NBSGG , NBSGB and NBSBG were prepared³ by condensing respectively N -benzenesulfonylglycylchloride with glycine, β -alanine and N -benzenesulfonyl β -alanylchloride with glycine in 1 : 1 molar proportions in aqueous solution at room temperature in weakly alkaline (pH 9–10) solution, adjusted by adding

aqueous NaOH solution with stirring. The resulting mixtures were cooled in ice-water bath and finally acidified with dil. HCl (pH 2). The *N*-benzensulfonamidodipeptide derivatives ($AH_2 = NBSGG, NBSGB$ or $NBSBG$, as the case may be) separated as shining white crystals, were purified by recrystallization from hot water, air-dried and analysed. The characteristic IR bands¹⁶ of the ligands in KBr phase due to COOH, CONH and SO_2NH groups were identified: COOH (1740–1710), amide-I (1640–1590), amide-II (1565–1535), amide-III (1285–1240), sulfonamide-I (1350–1320) and sulfonamide-II (1175–1155 cm^{-1}). All other reagents were of A.R. quality and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO_2 -free water. $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solution was standardized by combined ion exchange, acid-base and complexometric EDTA titrations at pH 4.5 using PAN indicator¹⁷.

The equilibrium measurements for the determination of formation constant of the 1 : 1 : 1 $Cu^{II} : AH_2 : B$ mixed ligands complexes involved pH-metric titrations¹⁸ of a series of solution containing known amount (0.01 *M*) of free HNO_3 and known amount (0.001 *M*) of the ligands AH_2 alone and in the presence of equimolar amount (0.001 *M*) of the B ligands in their protonated forms ($acH, bzH^+, glyH_2^+, bipyH_2^{2+}$ as the case may be) in the absence and in the presence of known amounts (0.001 *M*) of Cu^{II} -nitrate, with carbonate-free standard 0.1 *M* NaOH solution¹⁹. Initial volume of each solution was 25 ml and required amounts of $NaNO_3$ were added to maintain a constant ionic strength, $I = 0.1$ *M* ($NaNO_3$). All the solutions were allowed to attain equilibrium at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ (thermostated). The pH metric titrations were carried out under N_2 atmosphere.

pH was measured on a Systronics 335 pH meter using a special glass electrode in conjunction with a SCE. Analytical concentrations of hydrogen ion, corresponding to the pH-meter readings were calculated by following the usual procedure²⁰. Ionic product of water at the experimental temperature and the activity coefficient of hydrogen ion at the experimental ionic strength were obtained from literature^{21,22}. Electronic spectra of some of the metal ligand mixtures at appropriate pH values were recorded with a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded with a Parkin-Elmer 681 spectrophotometer.

Formation constant of the complexes were calculated by using the SCOGS programme² run on a IBM-300GL PC.

Estimates of some of the binary constants were obtained by the method of Irving and Rossotti¹⁸. The overall constants, β_{pqrs} were obtained as computer outputs, from which the other constants were calculated using the appropriate relations. Speciation curves (Figs. 1–4) of the complexes were also obtained as computer outputs and were used to elucidate the complex formation equilibria.

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